

1 **Assessing forwarder rolling resistance during salvage logging in mountain forest**

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8 **Abstract**

9 Logging operations in mountainous environments present unique challenges, especially in terms of machine-
10 soil interaction. The present study analyses the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) of a forwarder during uphill
11 logging operations in an alpine forest. Data was collected using a CAN-bus system that monitored the
12 operational parameters of the forwarder in real time, allowing a detailed analysis of the μ_{RR} under Rainy/No
13 Rain conditions and operational conditions (Winch/No Winch). Moreover, the μ_{RR} was evaluated against
14 moisture-sensitive areas obtained from Depth-To-Water (DTW) values interpolated for the area. The results
15 revealed that the rolling resistance coefficient is positively correlated with slope and rain, while inversely
16 correlated with DTW. A Random Forest model was used to explore the variability in the rolling resistance,
17 with a resulting R^2 of 0.96; amongst the most important variables there were slope, DTW and ruggedness.
18 These results suggest that μ_{RR} is a valuable proximal parameter to evaluate the machine-soil relationship, to
19 assess soil trafficability and to possibly optimize forest operations, with potential implications for forest
20 management practices and regulatory frameworks aimed at reducing soil compaction and environmental
21 impacts during logging activities.

22 **Keywords:** soil; rolling resistance coefficient; forwarder; salvage logging; CAN-bus

23 INTRODUCTION

24 The implementation of effective forest management requires a considerate balance between economic
25 productivity and environmental preservation, particularly when it comes to the use of heavy machinery in
26 forest operations. One key challenge is machine trafficability and impact, as forest soils are often sensitive to
27 compaction and rutting (Nazari et al. 2021), which can negatively impact tree growth (e.g. Ampoorter et al.
28 2011), water infiltration (e.g. Ampoorter et al. 2012), and soil physical properties (e.g. Labelle and Jaeger.
29 2011).

30 One of the most noticeable impacts of machine trafficability and passage is the formation of wheel ruts. To
31 prevent excessive damage, many countries (e.g., Germany - Act on the Protection against Harmful Soil
32 Changes and the Remediation of Contaminated Sites in Germany, Federal Soil Protection Act) regulate
33 acceptable soil disturbance through legislation, while international forest certification standards, such as the

34 *Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) and Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)* also
35 incorporate these considerations. These impacts are amplified when harvesting operations are performed in
36 already damaged environments, such as after a large disturbance: in this case, salvage logging operations
37 could augment the risks for soil exposure and erosion (Robichaud et al. 2020; Prats et al. 2021), as well as
38 fertility loss (Valipour et al. 2021). For example, the Northeastern Italian Alps have seen recent intensification
39 in machines trafficability due to large disturbances (Storm Vaia in 2018 and bark beetle outbreaks in the
40 following years) and subsequent logging operations conducted with ground-based heavy machinery (Cadei
41 et al. 2020; Udali et al. 2023), however prescriptions on forest roads and skid trails result still incomplete,
42 with lack of regional regulations on the trafficability of forest tracks.

43 Trafficability maps are key tools for forest operations, providing spatial information on terrain and soil
44 characteristics, and moisture conditions to assess machine mobility. A commonly recognized support method
45 in the planning of harvesting and forwarding operations is provided by predicting low soil bearing capacity
46 due to wet soil conditions (Hoffmann et al. 2022). One of the most adopted methods to assess that is through
47 the use of Depth to Water maps (DTW): these maps provide information regarding the depth and extent of
48 the water table relative to the ground surface, therefore providing information of possible surface overflow
49 (Salmivaara et al. 2020; Schönauer et al. 2021). These tools have seen extensive use in Boreal forests to
50 predict perennial streams, wet or water-saturated areas, and sensitive areas for ground-based trafficking
51 (Ågren et al. 2014, 2015). More recently, DTW maps have been documented to predict soil strength and areas
52 prone to higher machinery-induced compaction in Northern and Central European forests (Hoffmann et al.
53 2022; Guerra et al. 2024b), and also in Mediterranean forests (Latterini et al. 2022).

54 Another key factor influencing machine performance is the rolling resistance, defined as the friction force
55 that a vehicle must overcome to move forward (Suvinen and Saarilahti 2006), which depends on soil
56 properties and machine-soil interactions, directly affects energy consumption and machine mobility in forest
57 operations (Ala-Ilomäki et al. 2011; Mattila and Tokola 2019). Among soil and terrain properties, machine's
58 rolling resistance is mainly influenced by moisture content, slope gradient, and vegetation cover (Ala-Ilomäki
59 et al. 2020; Salmivaara et al. 2024). When machinery, such as forwarders, register higher rolling resistance,
60 this results in increased energy consumption, reduced productivity, and heightened risk of soil compaction
61 (cf. Ampoorter et al. 2012). Moreover, soil deformation and surface roughness further contribute to rolling
62 resistance, especially in off-road conditions typical of forest operations (Kurjenluoma et al. 2009), often
63 highlighted by repeated passages after extensive clear-cutting (Bygdén et al. 2003).

64 In steep terrain operations, winch-assisted, or tethered, logging has been developed to enhance the stability
65 and traction of forest machinery by providing additional support, therefore reducing wheel slippage and
66 distribute machine weight more effectively, leading to decreased soil disturbance and rut formation (Breinig
67 et al. 2025). Recent studies have demonstrated that winch-assisted harvesting offers a sustainable option for

68 utilizing highly productive machinery with reduced soil impact in steep terrain, up to 52% in slopes (Allman
69 et al. 2024).

70 To better understand rolling resistance and machine-soil interactions, modern machinery can be equipped
71 with CAN-Bus systems to monitor and record key machine parameters in real-time. These systems provide
72 valuable data on factors such as wheel speed, load, and engine performance, which can be used to calculate
73 rolling resistance and optimize operational efficiency. Ala-Ilomäki et al. (2020) reported how forest machines'
74 rolling resistance derived from CAN-bus data could provide useful information to map site trafficability during
75 machine work, therefore be able to predict machine mobility. Similarly, Salmivaara et al. (2024) showed how
76 harvester data collected at high resolution, with the joint use of DTW maps, can predict the occurrence of
77 extreme rolling resistance values. This information enables the authors to predict site trafficability for better
78 planning of timber extraction operations.

79 Moreover, environmental factors, particularly weather conditions, can contribute to significantly affecting
80 forest operations: precipitations, for instance, increase soil moisture, reducing soil bearing capacity and
81 increasing the risk of soil compaction and deformation, which in turn elevates the rolling resistance
82 (Melander et al. 2019). Frozen ground, for example, has been shown to have higher bearing capacity
83 providing less friction at machinery passage (Schönauer et al. 2022; Salmivaara et al. 2024).

84 When considering harvesting operations affecting largely disturbed forest areas, the combination of
85 environmental and climatic factors can create a challenging environment. Within this context, this study
86 ought to investigate the interactions between machine and soil in a mountain environment, characterized by
87 forest disturbance and moisture-sensitive terrain. Despite the extensive research on rolling resistance in
88 forestry, a few studies have explored its dynamics in salvage logging contexts, especially in mountainous
89 regions (cf. Hoffmann et al. 2022). This study builds upon previous research that explored the integration of
90 machine management data with soil, terrain, and climatic variables to estimate machines performance
91 (Guerra et al. 2024b). Additionally, it extends the investigation into the reliability of CAN-Bus data for
92 assessing forwarder rolling resistance under real working conditions (Guerra et al. 2024a).

93 In particular, this study aims to examine the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) of a forwarder during uphill
94 operations on skid trails in a forest heavily affected by bark beetle outbreak after a windthrow event.
95 Specifically, the study also aims to (i) compare μ_{RR} differences between winch-assisted and no-assisted
96 extractions, (ii) assess the impact on μ_{RR} of varying conditions due to rainfall and (iii) moisture-sensitive
97 terrain. Moreover, (iv) this study also aims to address the combined terrain and conditions effects on μ_{RR}
98 under real working conditions.

99 MATERIALS AND METHODS

100 MONITORED SITE AND CONDITIONS

101 The study took place in the Northeastern Italian Alps (N 46°18'24" – E 11°43'42"), located in the province of
102 Trento, at an altitude of 1650 m a.s.l. within the Paneveggio forest, owned by the Autonomous Province of
103 Trento (Figure 1). The forests consist of a typical spruce mountain forest, mainly composed of Norway spruce
104 (*Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst) and larch (*Larix decidua* Mill.), and an average growing stock of 425 m³·ha⁻¹. The
105 forest soil is heavily influenced by the presence of Dolomitic, volcanic and metamorphic rock, depending on
106 the area, providing a rich substrate for different herbaceous species to thrive, and the establishment of
107 multiple ecosystems and habitats. These areas were all impacted by the storm Vaia storm at the end of
108 October 2018, with consequent salvage logging operations, and by bark beetle outbreak (*Ips typographus* L.)
109 from 2022.

110 In particular, the selected study site was entirely composed of Norway spruce, with some larch, and the soil
111 was assessed to be clay loam with an organic horizon between 10–20 cm. The study site was subjected to
112 the outbreak at the beginning of summer 2023, and therefore the salvage operations were performed in
113 early fall of the same year (from 04/09/2023 to 03/10/2023), using ground-based machinery and Cut-To-
114 Length system. The timber was mechanically felled by a harvester machine and then extracted and
115 transported by a forwarder to the forest road. The forwarder used in this study was a John Deere model
116 1210E, a medium size category machine with loading capacity of 13 t (Brunberg 2004; Stankic et al. 2012).
117 The machine was equipped with off-road tires and traction tracks on both the front (Olofsforst ECO™ tracks,
118 Nordmaling, Sweden) and rear (Olofsforst Baltic™ tracks, Nordmaling, Sweden) bogies for steep field
119 operations, as well as with a synchronized traction aid cable winch (Figure 2). This machine configuration was
120 kept for the entire time during the logging operations, in all conditions. Further details are available in Table
121 1.

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123
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Figure 1. Distribution of the monitored skid trails in the study site. Skid trails' geometry has been simplified for the clarity of representation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

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126

Figure 2. Configuration of the monitored forwarder: (a) winch storage and anchor tree hook; (b) front traction tracks and (c) rear tracks.

127

Table 1. Details and technical specifications of the forwarder machine used in this study.

Model	Specific data
Engine	JD 6068 PowerTech™ Plus turbocharged, change air-cooled, 6 cylinders, 6.8 L displacement
Power	140 kW (1900 rpm)/189 SAE hp
Transmission	Hydrostatic-mechanical, 2-speed gearbox
Ground clearance	660 mm
Cylinders	6
Wheel number	8
Axles/Bogies	Heavy-duty Duraxle™ balanced-gear bogie axles at the front and rear. Hydromechanical differential lock at the front and rear.
Steering angle	44°
Weight empty	18,100 kg

129 DATA ACQUISITION AND PRE-PROCESSING

130 The data collection was based on a CANedge2 module datalogger from CSS Electronics. This module is
131 designed to interface with the primary communication network of the vehicle, the Controller Area Network
132 (CAN) bus, and record data from it. The module is also equipped with a Global Navigation Satellite System
133 (GNSS) antenna, enabling it to also record machine position. For this study, the machine's information
134 considered was date and time, position longitude and latitude coordinates, rotational engine (RPM), and
135 ground speed (m s^{-1}); all information was recorded with a frequency of 1 s. Additional information, such as
136 the use of the winch, was added based on field observations.

137 All data preparations and analysis were performed using R in the RStudio environment (version 4.4.1+
138 Chocolate Cosmos), with the resulting workflow summarized in Figure 3. From the position information, the
139 machine mobility was interpolated showing 15 main skid trails via QGIS; each of the trails was also identified
140 through field observations and assigned an identification number (id). Following the synchronization of each
141 monitored workday with the corresponding skid trail traversed by the forwarder, an initial comprehensive
142 dataset was generated detailing the skid trail characteristics for each work cycle.

143 Following previous results from Guerra et al. (2024a), to properly compute the μ_{RR} only uphill-unloaded
144 forwarder data was considered for each work cycle. This was performed to avoid including more variability
145 in the computation of the μ_{RR} due to variable payloads and assortments. In addition, frequent stops of the
146 forwarder due to the use of the log-loading grapple (downhill) are difficult variables to isolate in the CAN-bus
147 derived data. The information was isolated by automatically selecting a series of GNSS positions starting at
148 roadside (unloading zone) to the farthest point, i.e. the moment when the forwarder starts the loading work
149 phase.

150

151

Figure 3. A summary of the workflow followed for data collection and dataset implementation.

152 ROLLING RESISTANCE COEFFICIENT CALCULATION

153 The main attribute of interest for this study was to explore, in the described scenario, the rolling resistance, defined as the friction force that a vehicle must overcome to move forward (Suvinen and Saarilahti 2006), as described by previous research (Ala-Ilomäki et al. 2020; Salmivaara et al. 2024) (cf. Equation 1). The calculation of μ_{RR} is based on the forwarder equation describing the motion (Equation 2).

$$154 F_{RR} = \mu_{RR} \cdot N \quad (1)$$

$$155 F_{RR} = F_m - F_s \quad (2)$$

157 Where F_{RR} is the rolling resistance force, μ_{RR} is the dimensionless resistance coefficient, and N is the normal force; F_m represents the motive force, and F_s the slope force.

159 In this case, the motive force can be considered as the relationship between the expended power acting on the wheels (P_w) to move the vehicle at a certain velocity (v), as described by Equation 3.

$$160 F_m = P_w/v \quad (3)$$

161 On the other hand, the slope force can be determined by isolating the component parallel to the terrain of the vehicle weight (W) considering the slope angle (α) in the travel direction (Equation 4); whereas the normal component (N) is derived from Equation 5.

$$162 F_s = W \cdot \sin \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$163 N = W \cdot \cos \alpha \quad (5)$$

164 The slope force is subtracted from the motive force when driving uphill, as shown in Equation 2. Finally,
165 considering the normal force N acting on the machine, μ_{RR} was calculated by dividing the rolling resistance
166 force by the normal component of the vehicle weight (Equation 1).

167 DATASET IMPLEMENTATION

168 Specifically for this study, the motive force F_m was estimated using CAN-bus GNSS data, which provided the
169 vehicle's speed, necessary for converting the expended power into motive force (Equation 3). The slope
170 angle, and therefore the slope force (Equation 4) and the normal force (Equation 5), were determined by
171 extracting the terrain slope under the GNSS positions over the digital terrain model (DTM), available at
172 provincial level. Over the same DTM, the terrain ruggedness was interpolated and added as ancillary
173 information for each position.

174 Climatic data, specifically cumulative rainfall (mm), were obtained from the Province Meteorological Service
175 for the duration of the study period. Each skid trail was assigned a cumulative rainfall value based on the
176 days when the forwarder operated on that trail, and precipitation occurred.

177 The information related to the machine position and μ_{RR} was investigated in relation to the DTW (Depth to
178 Water) maps of the area. These maps provide information regarding the depth and extent of the water table
179 relative to the ground surface. To build the DTW map for the study area, the procedure described by
180 Schönauer et al. (2021) was followed.

181 In addition, the contribution of the trafficability of the area was considered by interpolating the number of
182 passages over the skid trails. In order to do so, starting from the CAN-bus derived information, the density of
183 recorded positions was determined through a KDE to obtain the area of transit of the machine during the
184 whole observed period. Then, the area was simplified into smaller polygons and for each of them the midlines
185 were automatically drawn using the package *midlines*. Finally, the midlines were brought together and used
186 with positions to assess the number of passages that occurred over each skid segment. This information was
187 then coupled with the main dataset based on the skid id reference.

188 All information then were collected into a dataset that was queried to provide data summary for each unique
189 skid trail through an iterative process. At the end of the process, for each skid trail several summary statistics
190 were calculated.

191 DATASET ANALYSIS

192 The analysis evaluated significant differences in the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) values distribution by
193 first checking for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, ideal for large dataset. Since the data did not
194 meet the assumptions for normality, the following statistical analysis was conducted using non-parametric
195 tests.

196 WINCH PRESENCE AND RAIN CONDITIONS

197 The information was grouped by either the presence/absence of the use of winch and then by the presence
 198 or absence of rain during the investigated period. In both cases, the differences were tested using a Mann-
 199 Whitney U Test. Moreover, the general hypothesis tested that, on average, the mean μ_{RR} values would be
 200 different in the case of the use and not use of tethered harvesting and in rainy/no rain conditions.

201 ANALYSIS OVER DTW AREAS

202 To investigate the influence of transit in water sensible areas, the machine positions were then coupled with
 203 DTW maps, the values extracted and divided into classes going from 0 (surface overflow of water) to 1 (no
 204 water) by intervals of 0.25. The values were checked through Kruskal-Wallis Test and Dunn's Test to evaluate
 205 the significance between classes.

206 ANALYSIS UNDER REAL WORKING CONDITIONS

207 Given the considerable number of observations available, the analysis under real working conditions was
 208 conducted by building a machine learning model using a random forest algorithm (RF), though a combination
 209 of functions available from the *ranger* and *caret* packages. The dataset was split following the 70/30 ratio for
 210 training and testing, with 2 variables to try at each split (*mtry*) and the optimal number of trees (*ntree*) of
 211 300. The validation was conducted using a 5-fold cross validation over the testing subset, and both the Root
 212 Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Pearson index (R^2) were computed, as well as the variable importance of the
 213 model.

214 RESULTS

215 ROLLING RESISTANCE COEFFICIENT OVERVIEW

216 The rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) results measured on the 14 skid trails in the salvage logging site are
 217 summarized in Table 2. The skid trail identified as skid 0 was entirely worked downhill, therefore it was
 218 excluded from the present analysis. The slope of the skid trails ranged between 21.6% and 31.4%, with the
 219 corresponding μ_{RR} values ranging from 0.09 to 0.23. When timber extraction was conducted with the aid of
 220 the winch system, the values recorded ranged between 0.10 and 0.14, similar to the business-as-usual, but
 221 averaging a higher mean slope compared to no winch-assisted trails. Figure 4 shows the relationship between
 222 the slope and the μ_{RR} per the different skid id, distinguishing the working conditions in which the winch-
 223 assisted extraction was performed.

224 **Table 2. Main results of the logged skid trails. The table includes the average slope, the average rolling resistance coefficient (μ_r),**
 225 **the indication if it was raining during the operations on the skid, and the winch's usage.**

Skid ID	Avg. Slope (%)	Avg. μ_{RR} (-)	Rain	Winch
1	23.5	0.09		
2	24.0	0.12		
3	21.6	0.12		
4	25.2	0.23	X	

5	24.8	0.17		
6	24.3	0.20	X	
7	24.0	0.14	X	
8	26.4	0.09	X	
9	23.8	0.09	X	
10	27.4	0.10	X	
<hr/>				
11	30.1	0.14	X	X
12	30.8	0.10		X
13	31.4	0.14		X
14	30.1	0.13		X

226

227

228 **Figure 4. Plot of mean μ_{RR} and mean slope across different skid trails. Also, the information of the use of the winch is reported.**

229 WINCH AND RAIN CONDITIONS

230 When it comes to the impacts of the different working conditions, the analysis was split between the use of
 231 the winch and the work performed on days that registered precipitation phenomena. The impact related to
 232 the use of the winch on μ_{RR} was further analyzed: the Mann-Whitney U test showed no statistically
 233 significant differences between the median values in skids with and without winch assistance (p -value =
 234 0.5018). This result suggests that while the winch provides traction assistance, the overall effect on rolling
 235 resistance may be limited, likely due to an increase in terrain slope (Figure 5A). However, winch-assisted skids
 236 had significantly steeper slopes, on average 30.5% compared to 24.4% for non-winch skids (p -value = 0.0015),
 237 indicating that the winch was predominantly used on more challenging terrain.

238 On the other hand, the statistical analysis displayed that rainfall had a significant impact on rolling resistance:
 239 skid trails that experienced rainfall exhibited notably higher μ_{RR} values, confirming the hypothesis that soil
 240 moisture increases rolling resistance (p -value < 2.2e-16) (Figure 5B).

241

242 **Figure 5. A representation of the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) under different conditions. (A) Comparison of values with and**
 243 **without the use of a winch; (B) Comparison of values in the presence and absence of rain.**

244 To further analyze the impact of weather conditions (Rainy vs. No Rain) on the rolling resistance, a detailed
 245 analysis was conducted by performing Mann-Whitney U test by selecting the data belonging to the skid trails
 246 that were exploited on rainy days as well as data from the same trails but exploited on no rainy days (Figure
 247 A 1b); after this, each skid was examined individually. The results (Figure 6 and Table A 1) revealed statistically
 248 significant differences in μ_{RR} upon the weather conditions examined for all skids ($p < 0.001$). In general, even
 249 in the trails where the difference in the mean values is very small, the statistical significance suggests that
 250 the effect is real and corresponds to differences that might be observed in the field. In all skid trails, with the
 251 exception of skid 11, the mean μ_{RR} value in Rainy conditions is higher than in dry conditions.

252

253 **Figure 6. : Boxplot showing the distribution of the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) for each skid trail under rainy (blue) and no**
 254 **rainy (red) conditions. The y-axis for each plot shows the rolling resistance coefficient.**

255 ROLLING RESISTANCE TREND OVER DTW AREAS

256 Regarding the rolling resistance values with respect to the DTW areas, the Kruscal-Wallis test provided highly
 257 significant differences between classes ($p < 0.001$). The following Dunn’s Test helped then to check for
 258 significant differences between the different classes, with results reported in Table 3. In general, the test
 259 statistics reflect how far apart the groups are in terms of standard deviations, with larger absolute values of
 260 the Z-statistics indicating larger differences between the groups considered. The class with DTW values higher
 261 than 1.00 has the largest differences compared to the other classes, with high significance. Additionally, μ_{RR}
 262 values in the lowest DTW class (0.00–0.25) are significantly different from coefficient values in larger DTW
 263 classes, and considerably higher in values (considering the negative difference). Therefore, the rolling
 264 resistance decreases with the increase of DTW values (closer to 1.00), with trails in wetter areas displaying
 265 higher μ_{RR} .

266 **Table 3. Dunn’s Test Z-statistic results for significant differences of μ_{RR} values between the DTW classes, with p-value adjusted**
 267 **using the Bonferroni method.**

DTW classes	0.00–0.25	0.25–0.50	0.50–0.75	0.75–1.00	1.00+
0.00–0.25		7.65 ***	12.85 ***	12.49 ***	35.50 ***
0.25–0.50			5.14 ***	4.25 ***	19.07 ***
0.50–0.75				-1.15 ns	10.72 ***
0.75–1.00					13.60 ***
1.00+					

268 Significance level: *** at $p < 0.001$; ns as for non-significant.

269 TREND IN REAL WORKING CONDITIONS

270 The RF model specs and results are shown in Table 4. Overall, the model was able to understand and explain
 271 most of the variance from the data, providing results with an accuracy of 96%. Moreover, it also produced
 272 low RMSE (0.04), providing predictions close to the real values interpolated from the CAN-bus data.
 273 Considering the importance of each variable used by the model in order to predict the rolling resistance
 274 coefficient, Slope and DTW values were the first and second most used, with the terrain ruggedness coming
 275 in third, and the rainfall information and the trafficability as last (Figure 7). This suggests that varying
 276 conditions such as rainfall might have a limited effect on explaining the μ_{RR} alone, considering the general
 277 picture of a medium period of monitoring; similarly, it could be said for the trafficability, i.e. the number of
 278 machine passages over the same trail segment.

279 **Table 4. Specifics and results from the RF model implemented to understand μ_{RR} variability.**

Training dataset size	375 930
Testing dataset size	93 979
RMSE	0.04
R ²	0.96

280

281 **Figure 7. Variable importance for the RF model used.**

282 DISCUSSION

283 The findings of this study highlight several key factors influencing the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR})
 284 during salvage logging in mountainous forest environments. The most notable result is the clear impact of
 285 both terrain features and weather conditions, confirming the role of μ_{RR} in depicting soil-machine
 286 interaction (Bygdén et al. 2003; Salmivaara et al. 2024). In particular, skid trails with steeper slopes
 287 consistently showed higher coefficient values, underscoring the role of gravitational forces in increasing
 288 rolling resistance. This result aligns with the established understanding that steeper terrain presents greater
 289 resistance to machinery movement due to both increased ground deformation and the energy required to
 290 overcome elevation gradients (Kurjenluoma et al. 2009; Hittenbeck 2013). More to that, the use of the winch
 291 on steeper slopes (greater than 28–30%) resulted in low rolling resistance values and potentially reducing
 292 the impact on the soil. Similarly, Breinig et al. (2025) registered comparable soil damage on winch-assisted
 293 and non-assisted timber extraction using a heavier machine but on a 3.5% slope; whereas Allman et al. (2024)
 294 findings highlighted that the use of a winch system in ground-based operations may mitigate the formation
 295 of rut depths, and in general soil disturbance, on steep slopes (up to 52%).

296 Regarding the influence of rainfall events on μ_{RR} , this was found to be significant in several skid trails (cf.
 297 Figure 6). Despite displaying on average, a higher value in the rolling resistance coefficient in rainy conditions,
 298 the data retrieved from skid 11 seemed to tell the opposite. In this case, possibly the use of the winch in
 299 assisting the operations could have contributed to reduce the effect of the precipitation and reducing the
 300 increase in value for μ_{RR} . In general, the results from the Mann-Whitney U test indicated that rainy
 301 conditions considerably increase rolling resistance, which is consistent with previous studies on the impact
 302 of soil moisture on terrain trafficability (Ala-Illomäki et al. 2020; Salmivaara et al. 2020, 2024). In a similar way
 303 to operations performed in agriculture, rainfall reduces soil bearing capacity, leading to greater soil
 304 deformation and compaction under the weight of heavy machinery (Gürsoy 2021), thus elevating μ_{RR} . This
 305 finding is critical when it comes to forest operations planning, as it highlights the need for adaptive forest
 306 management strategies to mitigate the impact of weather and climate change events on logging efficiency

307 (cf. Hoffmann et al. 2022). Following these findings, this study also ought to explore the possible connection
308 between μ_{RR} and surface moisture (i.e. DTW). In this case, the data recorded for the entire study period
309 showed that the larger the DTW value, the lower the rolling resistance. The finding gets partial confirmation
310 by the results obtained from the analysis for the Rainy/No Rain conditions, as well as validation from previous
311 findings in the literature (Salmivaara et al. 2020; Latterini et al. 2022).

312 With the intention of providing a more complete picture, a machine learning model was implemented using
313 random forest aiming to capture and describe most of the variability in the skid trails and in the site (recorded
314 through the CAN-bus) as well as the working conditions, both winch-assisted extraction and rainy condition.
315 The model performance, evaluated with the Pearson index (R^2), reached 0.96 in the attempt to describe the
316 μ_{RR} , with the major use of terrain-based variables (cf. Figure 7). The results obtained seemed reasonably
317 consistent compared to previous studies available in the literature: for example, in their study Salmivaara et
318 al. (2020) have modelled the rolling resistance for their site in southern Finland using a k-Nearest Neighbor
319 machine learning model fed with more than 60 variables, of which 26 were derived from topography and
320 terrain information. Their model performance reached 0.984 in modelling μ_{RR} . Similar studies with the aim
321 of defining possible effects on soil and, at the same time, simulating machine trafficability are more available
322 in literature. In Norway, Heppelmann et al. (2022) used the DTW to perform a logistic regression towards the
323 probability of severe rut formations, achieving encouraging results in terms of R^2 (0.19–0.23). Lidberg et al.
324 (2020) have compared different machine learning algorithms in order to generate wet area maps for planning
325 forest management operations, accomplishing reasonably high Kappa index (0.39–0.65) therefore getting a
326 good agreement of representation. In mediterranean forests, Latterini et al. (2022) have used DTW maps to
327 identify areas potentially sensitive to logging-induced disturbances: using non-metric multidimensional
328 scaling they were able to explain up to 97.5% of the variability in their test study area when it comes to
329 distinguish trafficable areas for forest operations.

330 All in all, the work has enlarged the understanding of the dynamics undergoing the machine-soil relationship
331 in salvage logging operations. Moreover, these findings were obtained in a challenging environment, such as
332 the Italian Alps, and considering some real-world conditions, i.e. the presence of rainfall during the monitored
333 period and the use of the winch. Therefore, they can also provide a simple yet comprehensive method to
334 evaluate the efficiency of operations, considering the machine's fuel parameters and production. However,
335 there were some issues the study did not address, either intentionally or fully.

336 i. *Additional vegetational variables.* The presence of additional aspects to consider in the
337 evaluation of the rolling resistance coefficient, such as the vegetation cover and the presence of
338 a brush mat. The presence of a layer of harvesting residues left on machine tracks can help
339 reduce wheel rut formation and can be beneficial at high traffic frequencies (Labelle et al. 2022).

- 340 ii. *Soil characteristics*. In this case, the orography of the terrain and its conformation were some of
341 the factors considered, although specific soil characteristics – for example soil type, texture and
342 organic matter content, among the others – might contribute in the understanding of the
343 variability in μ_{RR} and provide additional information of machine trafficability and potential
344 impacts (Heppelmann et al. 2022).
- 345 iii. *Machine and operational factors*. Considering the design of the study, the machine parameters
346 have been synthesized in determining μ_{RR} , therefore used as a proximal variable to understand
347 the machine-soil relationship. More variables could have been considered, but with the potential
348 risk of redundancy. However, machines from different manufacturers, resulting in diverse
349 characteristics, might have different behaviors and register different information, even on
350 comparable sites (cf. Cadei et al. 2020). Also, the design of this study voluntarily selected a fixed
351 configurations that did not change throughout the observed period, based on previous
352 experience (Guerra et al. 2024a) – i.e., one machine with specific track configuration, and
353 selecting uphill-unloaded data from the initial pool of information recorded by the CAN-bus
354 system.

355 CONCLUSION

356 The main aim of the presented study was to examine the rolling resistance coefficient (μ_{RR}) of a forwarder
357 during uphill operations in a forest heavily affected by bark beetle outbreak after a windthrow event. This
358 was performed by (i) comparing μ_{RR} differences between winch-assisted and no-assisted extractions, (ii)
359 assessing the impact on μ_{RR} of varying conditions due to rainfall, and (iii) moisture-sensitive terrain.
360 Moreover, (iv) this study also aimed to address the combination of these effects on μ_{RR} . The results indicate
361 that, in this case, there were no significant differences in the rolling resistance between winch-assisted and
362 not assisted trails, confirming that the use of the winch can reduce the potential impact of slippage and rut
363 formation. Regarding rainfall events and moisture-sensitive terrain, the registered and computed μ_{RR}
364 resulted higher compared to more dry conditions. In general, then, the machine learning model has provided
365 a high overall performance in modelling the μ_{RR} considering all the information provided ($R^2 = 0.96$), relying
366 more on terrain information and DTW maps. In this case, the model, built using only on morphological
367 parameters, provided useful information to understand more about potential trafficability and forest
368 machine use in salvage logging operations, with the aim of reducing the potential impact of such systems.
369 Future studies should aim to incorporate more comprehensive environmental monitoring (e.g., soil mapping,
370 remote sensing data) and operational details (e.g., different machine performance logs, operator behavior
371 tests) to develop a more holistic model. Additionally, controlled field experiments could help validate
372 observational findings and clarify causal relationships.

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382 DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

383 The author declares no conflict of interest related to this research.

384

(a)

(b)

386 **Figure A 1. (a) Rainfall precipitation within the study period considered. (b) Total rainfall and skid trails used during the same day.**

387

388 **Table A 1. Mann-Whitney U Statistic results for significant differences in Rainy and No Rain conditions over selected skid trails**
 389 **operated during rainfall events and not.**

Skid	U statistic	Significance ($p < 0.001$)
4	92207706	***
6	128978867	***
7	397772190	***
8	1684054	***
9	32248435	***
10	269489033	***
11	3861611	***

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